

Stress Related to Virtual Teaching among Teachers of Nursing Colleges

BY

Anakha Vincent¹ (Team Leader) Aarti Manjhi²

Aditya Fageria³; Agurla Lavanya⁴; Aleena Chacko⁵; Arshya Begum⁶; ArulMozhi⁷; Ashish Shergie⁸

Dissertation submitted to the

KALOJI NARAYANA RAO UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES UNIVERSITY IN WARANGAL,
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BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN NURSING

Under the guidance of
K. HARIKA PRIYANKA, ASSISTANT PROFESSOR
Apollo College of Nursing, Hyderabad
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CERTIFICATE

Certified that this is the bonafide work of
Ms. Anakha Vincent, Ms. Aarti Manjhi, Mr. Aditya Fageria, Ms. Agurla Lavanya, Ms. Aleena Chacko, Ms.
Arshya Begum, Ms. Arul Mozhi, Mr. Ashish Shergie

At

Apollo College Of Nursing Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

**Submitted in partial fulfillment of the requirement for the degree of Bachelor of Science in Nursing
from**

KALOJI NARAYANA RAO UNIVERSITY OF HEALTH SCIENCES UNIVERSITY IN WARANGAL,
TELANGANA.

Roll No: 1710407005, 1710407001, 1710407002, 1710407003;
1710407004, 1710407006,

Dr. S. Kanaka Lakshmi Principal
Apollo College Of Nursing Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

CERTIFICATE

I hereby certify that the present study entitled “**STRESS RELATED TO VIRTUAL TEACHING AMONG TEACHERS OF NURSING COLLEGES**” incorporates the results of the independent results of Ms. Anakha Vincent, Ms. Aarti Manjhi, Mr. Aditya Fageria, Ms. Agurla Lavanya, Ms. Aleena Chacko, Ms. Arshya Begum, Ms. Arul Mozhi and Mr. Ashish Shergiestudents of B.Sc Nursing 4th year 2019-2020 at Apollo College of Nursing, Jubilee hills, Hyderabad, designed and carried out under our guidance and supervision.

I also certify that it has not previously formed the basis for the award of degree, diploma or associate fellowship of the Kaloji Narayana Rao University of Health and Sciences or any other university before.

GUIDE

Mrs. K Harika Priyanka Assistant Professor
Dept. Obstetrics and Gynecology Apollo College of Nursing Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

RESEARCH COORDINATOR

Mrs. Archana Morey Associate Professor
Dept of Obstetrics & Gynecological Nursing Apollo College of Nursing Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad

**Submitted in Partial Fulfillment for the
Degree of Bachelor of Science in Nursing
At**

**Apollo College of Nursing, Jubilee Hills, Hyderabad
Kaloji Narayana Rao University of Health and
Sciences.**

AUGUST 2021

DECLARATION

We hereby declare that this dissertation entitled, has been prepared by us. It is the outcome of the original “**STRESS RELATED TO VIRTUAL TEACHING AMONG TEACHER OF NURSING COLLEGES**” research work undertaken and carried out us under the guidance and direct supervision of Mrs. K.Harika Priyanka, Assistant Professor, Dept. of Obstetrics and Gynecology, Apollo College of Nursing, Jubilee hills, Hyderabad.

We also declare that the material of this thesis is not found anywhere for the award of any degree, diploma or associate fellowship, previously of this university or any other university.

Roll No: 1710407005	Anakha Vincent
1710407001	Aarti Manjhi
1710407002	Aditya Fageria
1710407003	Agurla Lavanya
1710407004	Aleena Chacko
1710407006	Arshya Begum
1710407007	ArulMozhi B
1710407008	Ashish Shergie

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

SD	Standard deviation
%	Percentage
<i>F</i>	Frequency
χ^2	Chi Square
df	Degrees of Freedom
R	Reliability
NS	Not Significant
S	Significant
N	Sample Size

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ABSTRACT

The topic “stress related to virtual teaching among faculty of Nursing Colleges” was selected with the overall purpose of understanding the phenomenon of stress among faculty members and to find out how they cope stress operatively and strategically in higher educational institutions. The sample was taken by the stratified random sampling among nursing institutions.

The sample of research study included all teaching positions who were related to teaching with different designation as a Tutor, Lecturer, Assistant Professors, Associate Professors, and Professors. Seventy six percent of the respondents were women. The respondents’ responses were measured by the following Stressors: workload, situations at work, and relations with colleagues at work, efforts for students, work for organization benefits, and social acknowledgment with his status. The results exposed that the determining factor of stress between the administrators and teaching staff, with compiling of results, time burdens, infrastructure, student’s indiscipline and poor pay prospects are high ranked stressors. The conclusions also exposed that the administrators experienced, on a normal a low to moderate level of stress and this did not negatively affect their performance. This research will benefit the faculty to deal with work related stress.

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

“It is said that stress equals the distance between what you control over and what you are held responsible for”

The first thing that you must know about teaching as a profession is that teaching is about inspiring and motivating students to realize and exceed their potentials. The greatest teachers of all time have devoted their lives to inspiring and empowering their students to achieve great things and be good human beings.

Across the globe, the COVID-19 pandemic has brought substantial challenges on individuals and societies. As part of this, teachers have faced significant stressors in relation to their work. The pandemic required a very sudden shift to remote learning, and teachers were called upon to support students' academic development and well-being throughout this shift, while also navigating adversity and stress in their own lives.

Teaching is no longer merely hard work; it has become a highly stressful profession. The nature and organization of work makes teaching very difficult. Educators face new challenges and opportunities of the student population is increasingly diverse and needy. In the recent scenario demand of faculty members is to develop new knowledge and skills to perform virtual tasks rapidly for student's development. This often leads to overwhelming pressures and challenges for the faculty, which consequently leads to physical, psychological and emotional stress.

The aim of this research is to study the reasons for organizational stress among nursing faculties and to examine the correlation between stress and job satisfaction. The study will identify the main stressors and methods applied to manage them.

The study will be limited to various educational institutions demand its teaching fraternity to access virtual teaching only and the parameters for measuring the effects of stress were subjective rather than objective.

Stress has a different meaning for different people under different conditions. The first and most generic definition of stress was that proposed by Hanson Selye: “stress is the nonspecific response of the body to any demand. Other definitions have evolved to cater for different situations for example, cognitive. The article explores the basis for these definitions and their validity, and outlines the neuro-endocrine mechanisms that subserve the stress response. The concept of homeostasis, '**stability through consistency**' as the main mechanism by which the body copes with stress, has given way to allostasis, '**stability through change**' brought about by central neural regulation of the set points that adjust physiological parameters to meet the stressful challenge”.

A. Need For Study

The purpose of this study was to explore how returning to teaching during the Corona virus disease (Covid-19) pandemic impacted teachers' stress and anxiety. Specifically, the study investigated how teachers' anxiety changed during the pandemic. Additionally, the study explored the association of teachers' stress and anxiety and predictor variables for changes in teacher anxiety while teaching during the Covid-19 pandemic. Significant predictors of increased teacher anxiety included stress and communication within the nursing college, with virtual instruction teachers having the most increase in anxiety. Teachers are working as frontline workers during the pandemic; thus, schools and districts need to monitor teacher stress and anxiety during the Covid-19 pandemic and provide the necessary support. (Psyc Info Database Record (c) 2021 APA, all rights reserved).

In response to the Covid-19 pandemic, states have engaged in a delicate balancing act of opening their economies while simultaneously protecting public health since the first phase of stay-at-home orders last spring. While many workers have been tele-working and others have lost their jobs, some have been deemed “essential” by states, continuing to show up to work during the different phases of restriction states have implemented. Now, as states begin to decide how to prioritize the Covid-19 vaccine among their residents, the essential worker designation is more relevant than ever in states.

According to India Times, as for including teachers, their inclusion was discussed because school teachers were put on Covid-19 duty, sometimes even for 12 hours or more, as physical classes in schools across the city have been on hold since March 2020 year owing to the pandemic. Hundreds of teachers were helping the Government in food distribution during the migrant crisis and were also made in-charges of temporary shelter homes. Scores of other MCD and Government teachers are also involved in the government’s door-to-door survey program in detecting Covid-19 cases and now have been deployed for the upcoming vaccination campaign.

In addition, given the potential for subsequent waves of COVID-19 over the next few months and years—and indeed, different disruptions in the future—it is important to ascertain whether there are factors positively associated with teachers’ outcomes in these challenging times.

According to Lisa Federkeil, mastering distance teaching imposed by the COVID-19 pandemic was challenging for many teachers, in the present cross-sectional survey We assessed the level of stress that teachers experienced during the lockdown of schools in South India their strategies to cope with it external and internal barriers for distance teaching with an online questionnaire.

The impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on education included school closures and the implementation of virtual teaching and tele working without the knowledge or resources needed to do so. This situation accentuated the inequality in accessing quality education and generated high rates of stress, anxiety, and general discomfort in teachers. This study aimed to explore the mental health of teachers who were forced to telework because of COVID-19, and to analyze the association with socio-demographic, teacher-related, and working conditions. provide evidence suggesting the need for actions to improve the working conditions of teachers who telework in order to improve their mental health, and thus have a positive impact on the entire educational community.

B. PROBLEM STATEMENT

“Stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges”

C. OBJECTIVES

- To assess the stress related to virtual teaching among the faculty.
- To find out the association between the stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

D. OPERATIONAL DEFINITION

- **Assess:** It refers to the evaluation of stress related to virtual teaching among faculty through structured questionnaire.
- **Stress:** it refers to the type of change that causes physical, emotional and psychological strain as a part of virtual teaching
- **Virtual teaching:** Method of teaching that is taught either entirely online or elements of face to face courses are taught online through learning management system and other educational tools.
- **Teachers:** Body of educators who teach virtually. i.e. Professors or teachers

E. ASSUMPTIONS

- Faculty will have some stress in handling virtual teaching.
- Faculty may be cooperative and respond appropriately to the items of questionnaire.

F. HYPOTHESIS

- **Null hypothesis (Ho)** - There is no significant relationship between selected demographic variables and stress related to virtual teaching
- **Research hypothesis (H1)** - There is an association between stress and selected variables

G. DELIMITATIONS

- The study is limited to the various nursing institutions
- The data is collected within a limited period of time

H. VARIABLES

Research variable is the stress related to virtual teaching

I. CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK

Conceptual framework: It is a written or visual representation that serves as a spring board for theory development. A conceptual framework is defined as a network or a “plane” of liked concepts. Conceptual framework analysis offers a procedure of theorization for building conceptual framework based on grounded theory method.

The development of conceptual framework is a fundamental process which is required before conducting an actual research because it guides each stage of the process.

J. GENERAL SYSTEMS THEORY

General systems theory (GST) was outlined by Ludwig von Bertalanffy (1968). Its premise is that complex systems share organizing principles which can be discovered and modeled mathematically. The term came to relate to finding a general theory to explain all systems in all fields of science

Fig. 1: Conceptual Framework Based On General System theory (1995)

CHAPTER TWO

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Review of literature is one of the most important steps in the research process .it is an account of what is already known about a particular phenomenon. It provides a handy guide to a particular topic. According to American Nurses Association [2000] Review of literature is a body of text that aims to review the critical points of knowledge on a particular topic of research.

A. Review of literature about stress on virtual teaching

➤ *NATALIA VARGAS RUBILAR AND LAURA BEATRIZ OROS(26 NOVEMBER 2021)*

An empirical study with a cross-sectional design was developed, in which 9,058 Argentine teachers, who had to complete self-report measures, participated. The sampling method was non-random, using an online procedure of reclusion of volunteers. Descriptive techniques and non-parametric tests were used for data analysis. More than 60% of the educators reported high and moderately high levels of stress. The predominant stressors were uncertainty about the consequences of the pandemic, work overload and inadequate working environment. The more stress they perceived, the higher the manifestation of unwanted psychophysical symptoms. Professional burnout was higher for teachers with a higher load of stress and with more psychophysical indicators of discomfort. These results reveal the psychological impact of the COVID-19 pandemic on the education staff, and encourage the development of intervention measures to preserve the health of professionals. The study revealed that 62.1% of teachers in the sample display general levels of stress between moderately high and high.

➤ *CORTABARRIA, TRIANA AGUIRRE, EMILIO VERCHE AND ÁFRICA BORGES(11 November 2021)*

The aims of this study were to explore how teachers have been affected by the lockdown with respect to their mental health and their relationships in three main fields: work, family, and social relationships, and to know which is the role of physical activity in the mentioned variables. For that purpose, an online study was designed to collect quantitative and qualitative data. Results showed that indoor physical activity acts as preventive in lockdown situations, whereas the level of activity does not affect mental health. Also, teachers have experienced higher levels of distress due to the workload generated during the lockdown. A mixed methods design, known as the third paradigm has been used. It is characterized for including in the same research both quantitative and qualitative methods, specifying in the design the weight and the sequence of each part and explaining how both approaches are linked. The sample of this research was composed of 345 teachers with a mean age of 44.62 years (SD = 9.53; 264 women; 80 men; 1 preferred not to say) currently teaching in Spain in primary and secondary education.

➤ *A HASHEMI (2021)*

The present study aimed to investigate the opportunities, stress and challenges of online teaching in the higher education institutions of Afghanistan during the COVID-19 outbreak. It also explored the differences in the opportunities and challenges of online teaching according to gender, academic qualification (degree), and teaching experience. A simple random sampling technique was employed to collect the data from 628 university lecturers in Afghanistan. Descriptive statistics, independent sample T-tests and ANOVA tests were employed to investigate the research questions. The findings of the study has revealed some major opportunities, stress and challenges of online teaching. Besides, it was found that there was no significant difference in the opportunities of online teaching between genders, but a significant difference was obtained in the challenges of online teaching across genders. It was also revealed that academic qualifications and teaching experience has made a statistically significant difference in the opportunities obtained by the respondents. The qualification and teaching experience did not have any impact on the challenges of online teaching.

➤ *Florian Klapproth, Lisa Federkeil, Tanja Jungmann(2020)*

They have conducted a descriptive statistical study on level of stress that teachers experienced during the lockdown of schools in Germany, their strategies to cope with it, and external and internal barriers for distance teaching with an online questionnaire. Teachers were recruited for the study on the basis of nationwide professional networks. A total of 380 teachers from different school forms participated. They experienced medium to high levels of stress. More than 50 percent of them spent more than four hours daily on remote teaching, with secondary grammar school teachers experiencing significantly more stress and working more hours daily than special education teachers. The vast majority of them experienced technical barriers, but most of them felt able to cope functionally with the stress.

➤ *Teriwood & Chris Mclarthy (2020)*

Conducted study on emotional intelligence in academic learning. More than 5000 teachers responded to the survey conducted in Yale center, USA. The results indicated that teachers felt anxious, fearful, worried, overwhelmed & sad. Anxiety was the most repeated emotion by a landslide.

➤ *Dian Schafthavser(2020)*

Conducted study on educators feeling stressed, anxious, overwhelmed & capable. More than nine in ten teachers shifted to remote teaching in response to school closure. Among those who did switch to online teaching, respondents said they spend almost as much time preparing for their virtual classes as they did teaching them. Nine in ten agreed that the lack of face-to-face connection with students was making the transition "more difficult."

➤ *SUMMARY*

This chapter deals with the review of literature which includes studies about stress related to virtual teaching conducted among teachers across the world.

CHAPTER THREE

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research methodology is a systematical way to solve the research problem. It not only talks of the research method but also consider the logic behind the method. Research methodology describes a research approach, research design, setting, sample and sampling technique, development and description of tool, pilot study, procedures for data collection and plan for data analysis.

Present research is aimed at “Stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges”

A. RESEARCH APPROACH

The research approach is a broad based procedure for collecting data. The scientific method is a systematic approach to solve problem and expansion of knowledge.

The focus of the study is to assess the stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges. The research approach that is used for the study will be **quantitative- descriptive** in nature.

B. RESEARCH DESIGN

Research design is the Researchers overall plan for obtaining answers to the research questions. It spells out the basic strategies that the researcher adopt to gather information that is accurate and interpretable. Research design comprises methodological decisions that the researcher make to accomplish the objectives of the research project.

The research design adopted for the study is a descriptive survey design. Key:

A1- questionnaire

X- online survey A2- observation

Fig. 2: Systematic Representation of Research Design

Fig 3 : Systematic representation of research methodology

C. SETTING OF THE STUDY

Setting is a condition in which data collection take place in a study. The study was conducted at various nursing colleges

D. POPULATION

A population is the entire aggregation of cases that meets a specified set of criteria. Population means the entire set of individuals or object have some common characteristics. Target population is the aggregate of cases on whom the investigator would like to make generalization.

Accessible population is the aggregate of cases that confirm to the researcher as a tool of subject to conducting the study i.e, 100 teachers of various nursing colleges who teach or who have taught virtually and who were available at the time of data collection at selected Nursing Colleges

E. SAMPLE

Sample is a portion of the population who are selected for study or it is a subset of population elements. The sample in the study were teachers of various nursing colleges who teach or taught virtually

F. SAMPLE SIZE

- Sample size is the number of participants needed to achieve statistical conclusion validity. The number depends on the type of problem investigated precision required and the resources available. In the absence of a power analysis the safest procedure is to obtain data from as large
- a sample as is feasible
- The sample size consists of 100 teachers of various nursing colleges who teach or who have taught virtually.

G. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

Sampling Technique refers to the process of selecting a portion of the population to represent the entire population"

The sampling technique used in this study was convenient sampling. 100 samples were selected from a group of people easy to contact and sampling had the potential to reach the most vulnerable segment of the population, i.e, teachers of various nursing colleges. The self-structured questionnaire method used to assess the stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges

H. CRITERIA FOR SAMPLE SELECTION

The sample was selected based on the following inclusion criteria and exclusive criteria.

➤ INCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Teachers of nursing institutions
- Teachers those who are pursuing virtual teaching.
- Teachers who are available during study.
- Teachers who are willing to participate.

➤ EXCLUSION CRITERIA:

- Teachers who are not willing to participate.
- Teachers who are absent during data collection.

I. DESCRIPTION OF TOOL:

To assess the stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges of and the tool was designed in the form of self-structured questionnaire.

The tool consists of 2 sections.

- Demographic data
- Perceived Stress Scale to identify the stress among teachers of nursing colleges related to virtual teaching

J. Development and Description of the tool

The modified Perceived Stress Scale (PSS) is the most widely used psychological instrument for measuring the perception of stress. It measures the degree to which situations in one's life are appraised as stressful. Items were designed to tap how unpredictable, uncontrollable and overloaded respondents find their lives due to stress. The items are easy to understand, and the response alternatives are simple to grasp.

The following tool was used in assessing the level of stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges.

➤ Section-A:

Demographic variables

Demographic data include:-age, sex, educational qualification, designation.

➤ Section-B:

- Part 1: General questionnaire with multiple options

Data enquiring number of hours spent on virtual teaching, how long they teach virtually and what are the subjects they teach

- Part 2: Modified perceived stress scale

Perceived Stress Scale to identify the stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges.

There are 18 question items in the tool. Each item has its maximum scores to assess the stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges

K. Scoring procedure

➤ Stress

To assess the level of stress Perceived Stress Scale was used for each item; they are categorised into never, almost never, sometimes, fairly often, very often. Each item has its maximum scores

- never-0
- almost never-1
- sometimes-2
- fairly often-3
- very often-4.
- Individual scores on the Perceived Stress Scale can range from 0 to 72 with where score above 49 indicating higher perceived stress.
- The score interpretation will be 0-24: low stress level
 - ✓ 25-48: moderate stress level
 - ✓ 49-72: high perceived stress level

L. CONTENT VALIDITY

Content validity refers to the degree to which an instrument has an appropriate sample of items for the construct being measured and adequately covers the construct's domain.

The purpose is to determine validity, feasibility of the tool. The prepared tools were submitted to 2 experts for their suggestions, first expert has completed Ph.D in Obstetrics and Gynecological Nursing and second expert has completed M.Sc in Mental Health Nursing. Few modifications were made after the advice and discussion with the guide.

M. PILOT STUDY

Pilot study is a trial study carried out before a research design is finalized to assist in defining the research questions or to test the flexibility, reliability, and validity of the proposed research design.

The purpose of pilot study was

- To find out reliability of the tool.
- To find out feasibility of conducting the study.

It was the trial rehearsal for the main study. A formal permission was obtained from the Principal of Apollo College of Nursing, Hyderabad. The data collection was done from 15th December 2021 to 17th December 2021. The sample size of 10 samples was selected by using convenient sampling technique. The researcher introduced themselves and gave a brief introduction about the study through online. Thereafter the consent was obtained from each sample. The test was conducted by using Google Forms. The duration taken for pilot study was 1 hour and the data were collected by online survey method. Reassurance was provided that the data collected would be kept confidential.

N. RELIABILITY

Reliability refers to the ability of an instrument to create reproducible results or an instrument's reliability is the consistency with which it measures the target attribute.

The reliability was assessed by using Spearman Brown Coefficient. The value obtained was $r = 0.91$, which meant that the tool was reliable

O. MAIN STUDY:

The main study was conducted from 18th December 2021 to 22nd December 2021. The tool was prepared in English to collect the information from the study subjects. A brief introduction about the study was given and the consent was obtained from each subject as well as they were assured the confidentiality of their individual performance. The data relating to demographic variables, multiple choice questions (general questions) and perceived stress scale questions were collected by online survey method and their responses were received by the email.

P. PERIOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The period of data collection was for seven days from 18th December 2021 to 22nd December 2021

Q. PLAN FOR DATA ANALYSIS

Data was analyzed by using descriptive and inferential statistics.

➤ Descriptive:

- Statistics was used to analyze the demographic variables.
- Frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables.

➤ *Inferential statistics:*

- Chi square test was used to analysis the demographic variables and assess the stress related to virtual teaching.
- 1 hour and the data were collected by online survey method. Reassurance was provided that the data collected would be kept confidential.

R. SUMMARY

This chapter dealt with the methodology undertaken for the study. It included the research approach, research design, setting of the study, population, Sample, Sample size, sampling technique, inclusion criteria, exclusion criteria, description of the tool, content validity, pilot study, reliability, data collection, period of data collection and plan for data analysis.

CHAPTER FOUR

DATA ANALYSIS, INTERPRETATION AND DISCUSSION

Analysis is the appraisal of data and interpretation of the inferences that emerge from the findings of the study.

Interpretation of data consists of relating findings of the study to known facts. An important function of the process of interpretation is linking the findings of the study to the main stream of scientific knowledge in the concerned field.

The data was collected from 100 teachers of various nursing colleges. The objective of the study is to: To assess the stress related to virtual teaching among the teachers of nursing colleges, to find out the association between the stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

Descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages were utilized to describe sample characteristics. Inferential statistics such as chi-square test was used to find the association of structured stress related to virtual teaching.

A. *The objectives of the study*

- To assess the stress related to virtual teaching among the faculty.
- To find out the association between the stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

B. *Presentation of the data*

The data is presented in 2 sections:

➤ *SECTION -1*

Demographic data consists of age, gender, educational qualification and designation

➤ *SECTION- 2*

- Association table between level of stress and demographic variables.
- Frequency and percentage distribution of stress score regarding virtual teaching among teachers of nursing institutions.

SECTION- 1

IDENTIFY THE LEVEL OF STRESS RELATED TO VIRTUAL TEACHING AMONG TEACHERS OF NURSING INSTITUTION

Frequency and percentage distribution of demographic variables: Age, Gender, educational qualification, designation, Marital status, Place and Religion

n=100

Age	Frequency	Percentage
Below 25	26	26.0
25 – 35	58	58.0
Above 35	16	16.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 1: Frequency and percentage distribution of age

The table no. 1 reveals about the age of teachers, where teachers of below 25 years 26(26%),25-35years were 58(58%) and above35 years were 16 (16%)

Fig. 4: The Graphical Representation of Age

The figure 4 reveals about the age of teachers, where teachers of below 25 years 26(26%),25-35years were 58 (58%) and above35 years were 16 (16%)

n=100

Gender	Frequency	Percentage
Male	11	11.0
Female	89	89.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 2: The Frequency and Percentage distribution of gender

The table no. 2 reveals about the gender of teachers, where the female teachers were 89(89%) male teachers were11 (11%)

Fig. 5: The Graphical Representation of gender

The figure no 5 reveals about the gender of teachers, where the female teachers were 89(89)male teachers were11 (11%)

n=100

Educational Qualification	Frequency	Percentage
B.sc Nursing	41	41.0
M.sc Nursing	48	48.0
Ph.D in nursing	11	11.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 3: The Frequency and Percentage distribution of current occupation

The table no. 3 reveals about educational qualification of teachers B.sc nursing were 41%, M.sc nursing were 48% and Ph.D nursing were 11%.

Fig. 6: The Graphical Representation of educational qualification

The figure no.3 reveals about educational qualification of teachers B.sc nursing were 41%, M.sc nursing were 48% and Ph.D nursing were 11%.

n=100

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Tutor	44	44.0
Assistant Professor	38	38.0
Associate Professor	18	18.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 4: The Frequency and Percentage Distribution of Designation

The table no. 4 reveals about designation of the teachers in the institution, tutors were 44%, assistant professors were 38% and associate professors were 18%.

Fig. 7: The Graphical Representation of designation

The figure no. 7 reveals about designation of the teachers in the institution, tutors were 44%,assistant professors were 38% and associate professors were 18%.

n=100

No of hours spend in teaching	Frequency	Percentage
Less than or upto 2 hours	25	25.0
More than 2 hours	75	75.0
Total	100	100

Table 5: Frequency and percentage distribution of number of hoursspend in teaching

The table no.5 reveals about number of hour of spend in teaching, in that less than or upto 2 hours 25% and more than 2 hours 75%.

Fig. 8: The Graphical Representation of number of hours spent inteaching.

The figure no.8 reveals about number of hour of spend in teaching, in that less than or upto 2hours 25% and more than 2 hours 75%.

n=100

How long you are teaching	Frequency	Percentage
Less than 4 months	11	11.0
4 – 6 months	26	26.0
6 months-1 year	44	44.0
Above 1 year	19	19.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 6: The Frequency and Percentage distribution of how long theyare teaching

The table no. 6 reveals about how long they are teaching, in that less than 4 months were11%, 4-6 months were 26% , 6-1 year were 44% and above 1 year were 19%.

Fig. 9: The Graphical Representation of how long they are teaching virtually

The figure no. 6 reveals about how long they are teaching, in that less than 4 months were 11%, 4-6 months were 26% , 6-1 year were 44% and above 1 year were 19%.

n=100

Subject taught by selected teachers	Frequency	Percentage
Medical Surgical Nursing	13	13.0
Mental health Nursing	10	10.0
Nursing Foundation	18	18.0
Child Health Nursing	6	6.0
Community Health Nursing	22	22.0
Nursing Management	5	5.0
CET	2	2.0
Obstertical and Gynecological Nursing	15	15.0
Nutrition	6	6.0
Nursing Research	3	3.0
Total	100	100.0

Table 7: The Frequency and Percentage distribution of subject taught byselected

The table no. 7 reveals about the subject taught by selected teachers, in that medical surgical nursing were 13% , mental health nursing were 10%,nursing foundation were 18%, child health nursing were 6%, community health nursing were 22%, nursing management were 5%, CET were 2%, OBG were 15%,nutrition 6% and nursing research were 3%.

Fig. 10: The Graphical Representation of subjects taught by selected teachers

The figure no. 7 reveals about the subject taught by selected teachers, in that medical surgical nursing were 13% , mental health nursing were 10%,nursing foundation were 18%, child health nursing were 6%, community health nursing were 22%, nursing management were 5%, CET were 2%, OBG were 15%,nutrition 6% and nursing research were 3%.

SECTION - 2**ASSOCIATION BETWEEN THE LEVEL OF STRESS REGARDING VIRTUAL TEACHING WITH SELECTED DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES.**

S.NO	Demographic Variables	Stress level			Calculated χ^2	df	Table value	Significance
		Mild	Moderate	Severe				
1.	AGE							
	Below 25	6	17	3	4.420	4	0.352	S
	25-35	10	41	7				
	35-45	2	9	5				
	Above 45	18	67	15				
2.	Gender							
	Male	4	3	4	8.988	2	0.011	S
	Female	14	64	11				
	other	18	67	15				
3.	Educational qualification							
	B.sc nursing	8	24	9	5.122	4	0.275	S
	M.sc nursing	9	33	6				
	Ph.D in nursing	1	10	0				
4	Designation							
	Tutor	7	27	10	4.970	4	0.290	S
	Assistant professor	8	28	2				
	Associate professor	3	12	3				
5	Number of hour spend in teaching							
	Less than or upto2 years	8	15	2	4.962	2	0.084	S
	More than 2 hours	10	52	13				
6.	How long you are teaching							
	Less than 4 months	5	6	0	15.393	6	0.017	S
	4-6 months	7	15	4				
	6-1 year	5	34	5				
	Above 1 year	1	12	6				

Table 9: Association between level of stress and demographic variables

H01- There is association between level of stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables that are age, gender, educational qualification designation, number of hours spend in teaching and how long they are teaching

The obtained chi square value for the association of stress level and age is 4.420 which is greater than the table value 0.352 at the level ($p \leq 0.05$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is significant association between stress level and age.

The obtained chi square value for the association of stress level and gender is 8.988 which is greater than the table value 0.011 at the level ($p \leq 0.05$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is significant association between stress level and gender

The obtained chi square value for the association of stress level and educational qualification is 5.122 which is greater than the table value 0.275 at the level ($p \leq 0.05$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is significant association between stress level and educational qualification.

The obtained chi square value for the association of stress level and designation is 4.970 which is greater than the table value 0.290 at the level ($p \leq 0.05$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is significant association between stress level and designation

The obtained chi square value for the association of stress level and number of hours spend in virtual teaching is 4.962 which is greater than the table value 0.084 at the level ($p \leq 0.05$). Hence null hypothesis is rejected. This shows that there is significant association between stress level and number of hours spend in virtual teaching

The obtained chi square value for the association of stress level and how long they are teaching is 15.393 which is greater than the table value 0.017 at the level ($p \leq 0.05$). Hence the null hypothesis is rejected. This shows there is significant association between stress level and how long they are teaching.

C. SUMMARY

This chapter deals about the data analysis which includes frequency and percentage distribution of sample characteristics, assessment of level of knowledge, assessment of level of stress and association between levels of knowledge with demographic variables.

CHAPTER FIVE

DISCUSSION, SUMMARY, CONCLUSION IMPLICATIONS, RECOMENDATIONS, LIMITATIONS

This chapter deals with the discussion, summary of the study, it's findings and conclusion about the study to assess the stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing institution. The limitations are put forward and recommendation is suggested.

Analysis is appraisal of data and interpretation of inferences that emerge from findings of study. Data was collected from 100 teachers of different nursing institution. The data is presented in 2 sections:

- **Section 1:** Demographic data
- **Section 2:** Perceived Stress Scale to identify the stress among teachers of nursing colleges related to virtual teaching.

A. DISCUSSION

Teriwood & Chris Mclarthy (2020)

Conducted study on emotional intelligence in academic learning. More than 5000 teachers responded to the survey conducted In Yale center, USA. The results indicated that teachers felt anxious, fearful, worried, overwhelmed & sad. Anxiety was the most repeated emotion by a landslide.

B. OBJECTIVES

- To assess the stress related to virtual teaching among the faculty.
- To find out the association between the stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

C. Major Findings of the Study

Findings related to description of sample characteristics

Data was collected among 100 teachers of nursing institution, who were teaching virtually during pandemic effects of covid - 19. The present study show that majority of teachers (58%) belongs to 25-35 years age group. The table no. 1 reveals about the age of teachers, where teachers of below 25 years 26(26%), 25-35 years were 58(58%) and above 35 years were 16(16%)

The table no. 2 reveals about the gender of teachers, female teachers were 89(89%) male teachers were 11(11%)

The table no.3 reveals about educational qualification of teachers of B.Sc Nursing were 41%, M.Sc Nursing were 48% and Ph.D Nursing were 11%.

The table no. 4 reveals about designation of the teachers in the institution, Tutors were 44%, Assistant Professors were 38% and Associate Professors were 18%.

The table no.5 reveals about number of hour of spend in teaching, in that less than or upto 2 hours 25% and more than 2 hours 75%.

The table no. 6 reveals about how long they are teaching, in that less than 4 months were 11%, 4-6 months were 26% , 6-1 year were 44% and above 1 year were 19%.

The table no. 7 reveals about the subject taught by selected teachers, in that Medical Surgical Nursing were 13% ,Mental Health Nursing were 10%,Nursing Foundation were 18%, Child Health Nursing were 6%, Community Health Nursing were 22%, Nursing Management were 5%, Communication Education and Technology were 2%, Obstertical and Gynecological Nursing were 15%, Nutrition 6% and Nursing Research were 3%.

There is association between level of stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables that are age, gender, educational qualification designation, number of hours spend in teaching and how long they are teaching.

Association between level of stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

A significant association was found for certain demographic variables such as age, gender, educational qualification, designation, no of hours they teach virtually and how long they teach virtually

D. SUMMARY

The pandemic has not only affected the mental state of students since teachers have also accumulated a high level of stress since the beginning of the crisis. The studies have pointed out that during lockdown, teachers have suffered stress from having to adapt (in record time) in order to provide online classes. This stress has often been accompanied by symptoms of anxiety, depression, and sleep disturbance as a consequence of the increased workload resulting from home teaching

Not many studies conducted during the pandemic measure the symptoms of stress, anxiety, and depression among teachers but the studies that have been carried out suggest that they have psychological symptoms and this reinforces the importance of reopening schools and universities. The study has indicated that this crisis has caused teachers to suffer problems that are often related to a pandemic situation, such as anxiety, depression, domestic violence, and divorce, all of which restrict their ability to teach properly. The study assessed the prevalence of anxiety among teachers and found a prevalence of 13.67%, with women being more anxious than men and the older ones being more symptomatic. The sample in the study was teachers of various nursing colleges who teach or taught virtually. The sample size consists of 100 teachers of various nursing colleges who teach or taught virtually. To assess the level of stress Perceived Stress Scale was used for each item. Another study conducted in March in China showed that the prevalence of stress symptoms in teachers was 9.1% and that it was important to support them psychologically

Moreover, the studies have found that working from home using Information and Communication Technologies (ICT) can create feelings of tension, anxiety, exhaustion, and decreased job satisfaction and in times of a pandemic these were the only tools that were available to teachers.

E. CONCLUSION

Members of the teaching profession experienced psychological discomfort at the beginning of the new 2020–2021 academic year. This symptomatology has been found to be higher in women than in men, but contrary to our expectations, was found to be higher in older people and in teachers of infant and primary education. As expected, people with job instability are those who have suffered the most psychological symptoms. These findings indicate the importance of safeguarding the mental health of teachers to ensure both the well-being of students and high quality teaching. Therefore, special psychological care should be given to those teachers that are most vulnerable to the impact of this pandemic, so that they could better cope with this crisis, and consequently perform better in their teaching role. In short, we must bear in mind that the education received by young people in this current time of crisis will shape the society of the future. Therefore, if we want this education to be of a high standard, then we must protect the psychological well-being of the people who provide it. In conclusion, stress was highly prevalent in teachers and it also affects teachers as manifestation in different systems so measures need to be taken to reduce stress level that is meditation, making job enrichment and other stress reduction techniques to prevent burnout. Teacher's stress can affect teaching learning process and patient care so timely management is applied through concern authority is needful.

F. NURSING IMPLICATIONS

The implication of the study seen in the:

➤ *Nursing Practice*

The nursing personnel can develop skill in helping the pupil from falling into stress which leads to various health issues including depression. Also, nursing personnel can give awareness about maintaining good mental health

➤ *Nursing Administration:*

Nursing administration should take an initiative in creating policies and plans in providing education to the people and involve them in relief of their problems.

➤ *Nursing Education:*

Education plays an important role in identifying health problems. Regular health screening program and educational programs can be conducted so that health of the public can be focused by health care workers. The public can be educated regarding identification of stress and strategies to adopt the preventive measures.

➤ *Nursing Research:*

A profession seeking to improve the practice of its members and to enhance its professional stature strives for continued development of a relevant body of knowledge. Nursing research represents a critically important for nursing profession to acquire such knowledge. Nursing researchers should be aware about the existing communication skills, psychological therapies and status of nursing profession. Nursing research helps us to do research in large population and we can educate the people regarding the identification and management of stress.

G. LIMITATIONS

- The study was limited to the selected nursing colleges.
- The study was limited to small number of sample (100).
- The study was limited to short period of time (5 days), if it was done for more days more samples could have participated in the study.

H. Recommendations :

Based on the findings of the study the following recommendations are put forward for the further research:

- Similar study can be taken on larger sample to generalize the findings.
- A study could have done in all the college In South India rather than selected colleges.
- A similar study can be done to assess the knowledge regarding stress coping mechanism.

I. SUMMARY

This chapter reveals that the present study identified that there is a significant association between level of knowledge and demographic variables

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ANNEXURES 1

To,

.....,
.....,
.....

Subject: Requesting permission for Research - Pilot Study

Respected Madam/Sir

This is to bring to your kind notice that we GROUP 1 B.Sc. Nursing 4th year students, Apollo College of Nursing Hyderabad would like to conduct main study and collect data among faculty on the topic “A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges “for research purpose. From 01 /07/2020 to 03/07/2020 as a partial fulfillment of Bachelor of Science in Nursing requirement from KNR University.

Problem statement:

A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges

Objectives:

- To assess stress related to virtual teaching among faculty
- To find an association between the stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

Kindly grant permission for the same
Thanking you,
Yours sincerely,

.....
.....

ANNEXURE – II

.....,
.....,
.....

Subject: Requesting permission for Research - main study

Respected Madam/Sir

This is to bring to your kind notice that we GROUP 1 BSc. Nursing 4th year students, Apollo College of Nursing Hyderabad would like to conduct main study and collect data among faculty on the topic. “A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges” for research purpose. From 13/12/2020 to 18/12/2020 as a partial fulfillment of Bachelor of Science in nursing requirement from KNR University.

Problem statement:

A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges

Objectives:

- To assess stress related to virtual teaching among faculty
- To find an association between the stress related to virtual teaching and selected demographic variables

Kindly grant permission for the same Thanking you,
Yours sincerely,

.....

ANNEXURE –III

LETTER SEEKING EXPERTS OPINION ON CONTENT VALIDITY OF TOOL

From, Group 1
4th year B. Sc Nursing Apollo College of Nursing, Jubilee Hills,
Hyderabad To,,

Through the Principal, **Subject : Expert opinion on content validity of tool.** Respected Sir / Madam,
We are doing a project work on **“A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges.”** For partial fulfillment of our Bachelors of Nursing, under Kaloji Narayana Rao University of Health and Sciences. Henceforth we are requesting for your expert opinion, kindly go through the tool and give valuable suggestions.

We also request to certify our content if you feel that we can continue our study with modification and suggestions.

Thanking you

Yours Sincerely,

Signature of Guide:

PRINCIPAL:

ANNEXURE-VI**CERTIFICATE OF VALIDATION**

This is to certify that the tool developed by Group 1, B.sc Nursing 4th year students of Apollo College of Nursing, Hyderabad is validated by under signed and can proceed with this tool with suggested modification before conducting main study for dissertation entitled ason “**A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges.**”

Name :

Designation :

Date :

Signature :

ANNEXURE-V

LIST OF EXPERTS WHO VALIDATED THE TOOL

- 1) Dr. A. JABILA
GNANATHIAH
PROFESSOR
HOD (Obstetrics and Gynecology
Department)ACON

- 2) MRRS.JANUARY
SMILESASSOCIATE
PROFESSOR
HOD (Mental Health Nursing
Department)ACON

ANNEXURE-VI

INFORMED CONSENT TO PARTICIPATE IN RESEARCH

Dear participant,

We, Group1, B.Sc. nursing students of Apollo College of Nursing Hyderabad, as a part of our research study on **“A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing colleges.”**

As a representative of this study, we have explained to the participant the purpose, the procedure, the possible benefits of the research study, and how privacy will be protected.

You have been informed about the study’s purpose, procedures, and possible benefits, and how your privacy will be protected

You have been given the opportunity to ask questions before you sign.

Participant signature Date

TOOL

A RESEARCHER MADE PERCEIVED STRESS SCALE TO ASSESSTHE STRESS RELATED TO VIRTUAL TEACHING AMONG TEACHERS OF NURSING COLLEGE

CONSENT FORM

- 1. I understand that all the information about me will be kept confidential**
 - 1) Yes
 - 2) no
- 2. I understand that the information from this research will be published but I'llnot identify as a participation in this research in any population**
 - 1) Yes
 - 2) No
- 3. I agree to take part in the above study**
 - 1) Yes
 - 2) no

Problem Statement

"A study to assess stress related to virtual teaching among teachers of nursing college"Dear respondent,

- Read each question carefully
- Choose the option which seems to be the most appropriate for you
- Ensure that you do not miss out any questions

The questionnaire consists of two parts

Part 1: demographic data

Part 2: researcher made perceived stress scale

SECTION A

DEMOGRAPHIC DATA

**Sample
No:**

A. What is your age?

- Below 25
- **25-35**
- 35-45
- **Above 45**

B. What is your gender?

- Male
- Female
- Other

C. What is your educational qualification?

- BSC Nursing
- MSC Nursing
- PHD in nursing

D. What is your designation?

- Tutor
- Assistant professor
- Associate professor
- Professor
- Lecture

E. No of hours spend for virtual teaching?

- Less than or up to 2hours
- More than 2 hours

F. Since how long are you teaching virtually?

- Less than 4 months
- **4-6months**
- 6 months to 1 year
- **More than 1 year**

SECTION B**A RESEARCHER MADE PERCIEVED STRESS SCALE**

Sl. No	Statements	Never	Almost never	Sometimes	Fairly often	Very often
1	I have constant time pressure to complete the chapters due to technical failures happening while teaching.	0	1	2	3	4
2	I feel stressed due to interruptions and disturbances while performing my job.	0	1	2	3	4
3	I am worried about the practical knowledge of the students as the knowledge is passed through very small window	0	1	2	3	4
4	I feel anxious about not receiving appropriate response from the students even after spending hours in online classroom.	0	1	2	3	4
5	I feel my effort is not worthy as I don't get enough response from students.	0	1	2	3	4
6	I have experienced an undesirable change in my work situation due to the establishment of new method of teaching	0	1	2	3	4
7	I feel stressful to take classfrom home.	0	1	2	3	4
8	I feel stressful to waste more of my class time in checking the presence of students	0	1	2	3	4
9	I feel stressed about the health issues accompanied by long time usage of technology	0	1	2	3	4
10	I am nervous to conduct online classes, because am not so good in using technology	0	1	2	3	4
11	I feel worried about the technical failures which disrupts the continuity ofmy class	0	1	2	3	4
12	I feel anxious when I start thinking about difficulty inassembling all the studentsfor the class	0	1	2	3	4

13	When I get home, I can easily relax and spend mytime with peace (reverse coding)	4	3	2	1	0
14	I feel disturbed about the malpractices performed bystudents while conducting an online exam	0	1	2	3	4
15	I feel very comfortable topresent a class online (reverse coding)	4	3	2	1	0
16	I am stressed about the lack of control I have overthe class while I teach virtually	0	1	2	3	4
17	I strongly feel the classroom ethics have beencompromised to great lengths including regularity of the students	0	1	2	3	4
18	Work life balance is good when I am working fromhome. (reverse coding)	4	3	2	1	0

SCORE INTERPRETATION

- Score ranging from 0- 24 is considered as low stress
- Score ranging from 25-48 is considered as moderate stress
- Score ranging from 49-72 is considered as high perceived stress